

Bridging phases towards the Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological Research Infrastructure

Report on mapped workflows in period 1

Deliverable D1.1

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Acronyms

3PDP	3rd Party Data Provider
CI	Cyberinfrastructure
CDN	Central Data Node
DAR	Digital Asset Registry
DEIMS-SDR	Dynamic Ecological Information Management System - Site and dataset registry
DiV	Discovery and Visualisation tool
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DP	Data Provider
DS	Data Steward
DU	Data User
eDM	eLTER Data Manager
eLTER DiV	eLTER Data and Integrated Visualisations
eLTER CDN	eLTER Central Data Node
eLTER PPP	eLTER Preparation Phase Project
eLTER PLUS	Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological Research infrastructure Advanced Community project
eLTER RI	eLTER Research Infrastructure
eLTER CL Vocab	eLTER Controlled Lists Vocabulary
eLTER SO Vocab	eLTER Standard Observation Vocabulary
ENVRI	European Environmental Research Infrastructures
EnvThes	Environmental Thesaurus
EO	Earth Observation
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable and Reusable
HO	Head Office
IC	Interim Council
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
NRI	National Research Institution
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PID	Persistent Identifier
RA	Remote Access

SE	System Engineering
SO	Standard Observation
SP	Service Portal
SPI	Site Principal Investigator
TC	Topic Centre
TOGAF	The Open Group Architecture Framework
TSA	Thematic Service Area
TA	Transnational Access

Summary

A key goal of the eLTER EnRich project is to create a comprehensive framework for the future implementation of the eLTER Research Infrastructure (RI). This framework is fundamentally based on adopting a Systems Engineering Approach to design and implement the delivery of the RI's services. The project follows an Agile development methodology, where a so-called skeleton infrastructure is first implemented to demonstrate a minimum viable eLTER cyberinfrastructure covering the minimum requirements that allow the research infrastructure to start providing services to stakeholders. At the same time, the project will explore how to prioritise the enrichment of the skeleton with more advanced features as plans crystallise during the process. This approach will support decision-making by evaluating various opportunities and pathways for connecting stakeholder needs, user requirements, technical solutions, and the distribution of services among hosting organisations.

An initial step in developing an operational framework involves streamlining the knowledge generated in the eLTER PPP and eLTER PLUS projects. The knowledge base established in these projects covers numerous aspects essential for the RI's construction, including stakeholder mappings, feedback from the eLTER community, and an initial outline of a potential service portfolio. Additionally, some conceptual data workflows related to Standard Observations and high-level data products enrich the legacy of these projects.

Building on this foundation, the objective of the present document is to focus on services identified and selected as priority services by the Interim Council, the RI's decision-making body, and to outline the necessary workflows required for their delivery. By employing the Systems Engineering Approach, we map the workflows needed to provide these key services in standardised, actionable, machine-readable formats to inform the overall System Engineering setup and implementation planning.

This mapping process includes detailed documentation of the steps, roles, and responsibilities required to support specific end-to-end workflows. Users' requirements thereby define the necessary RI functions and information flows, which are evaluated to derive appropriate solutions. These solutions then guide the implementation planning for integrating other infrastructure capabilities and determine the final distribution of service-hosting organisations.

This document combines information associated with different views of a selection of services identified as 'core' services. That includes the stakeholders' perspective and the main business roles necessary for the implementation of the service provision, linking the service workflows to the main components and functionalities of the eLTER Cyberinfrastructure (CI). The workflow representation is provided with the appropriate level of detail to serve the purposes of both the System Architecture planning and the technical design of the CI. It serves as a blueprint for the Cyberinfrastructure team to design the System Architecture, aligning the ICT infrastructure with service-oriented aspects according to the overall eLTER strategy for the RI construction. We aimed to provide sufficient detail to support effective collaboration with the Cyberinfrastructure team while allowing for enough flexibility to account for changes in services and infrastructure structure motivated by different service hosting solutions.

1. Introduction

eLTER EnRich aims to make a significant contribution to the eLTER ESFRI process by bridging the gap between the preparatory and operational phases of RI construction. eLTER EnRich capitalises on the legacy of many projects, the most advanced ones being eLTER PPP and eLTER PLUS¹. These two projects have been working in parallel since 2020 to set the foundations of the eLTER RI.

A first milestone by eLTER PLUS a and eLTER PPP has been achieved with the adoption of the eLTER vision in 2021 by 19 countries represented by ministerial delegations in the eLTER Interim Council: *“eLTER RI (the integrated European Long-term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological Research Infrastructure) is a pan-European research infrastructure dedicated to long-term multidisciplinary ecosystem studies, filling a major gap identified in the environmental RIs (ENV-RIs) landscape. eLTER responds to the challenge of understanding the complex interactions between humans and nature over the long term. Environmental sustainability can only be achieved on the basis of robust knowledge and empirical evidence needed to identify and mitigate human impacts on ecosystems and to understand how ecosystems can support a future resilient society. eLTER catalyses scientific discovery and insight through its state-of-the-art research infrastructure, collaborative working culture and transdisciplinary expertise. This enables the development and application of evidence-based solutions for the well-being of present and future generations.”* The vision provides a clear hint into the complexity of this endeavour and the amplitude and diversification of the knowledge base that RI will contribute to build, manage and share. Over the past four years, the two projects have played a pivotal role in defining the content and delineating the boundaries of this knowledge base, which encompasses all ecosystem spheres (geosphere, hydrosphere, biosphere, atmosphere, and socio-sphere) and integrates data and information from a multitude of sources.

A key challenge in implementing the eLTER Research Infrastructure (RI) is delivering a range of services provided to the user community. These services are designed based on specific objectives and processes that need to be clearly defined. This clarity is essential for the eLTER Cyberinfrastructure to effectively integrate the necessary technologies and ensure their successful implementation. The process hinges on two essential features: it must be i) iterative and ii) leverage modularity to better adapt to the continuously evolving definitions of roles, tasks, and responsibilities of the organisations applying to host the RI services. The EnRich project follows the Agile² methodology, which divides the project into manageable phases. In this approach, solutions are designed, developed, and tested through iterative cycles, where each stage, or “sprint”, generates feedback for improvements in the next iteration. The ultimate goal is to build a “skeleton-infrastructure”—a minimum viable product—capable of delivering an initial set of services, defined as Core Services, and later the Other Services (Mallast et al, 2024), while also leaving space for further development to enrich the future RI services with more advanced features in this fast-developing landscape.

The main objective of this report is to contribute to the implementation of this iterative process by providing a consistent mapping of the workflows of the services, i.e. a representation of the processes to be executed to provide those services. In the followings, we use the term “service workflow” to identify the representation of what is more often defined as a “business process³”, i.e the sequence of steps or tasks required to complete a process, consisting of multiple workflows, and often involving both human and automated actions. The mapping of the service workflows is key to a sound and service-oriented⁴ system

¹ <https://elter-ri.eu/projects>

² <https://agilemanifesto.org/>

³ <https://www.ibm.com/think/topics/workflow#:~:text=A%20workflow%20is%20a%20system%20for%20managing,processing%20information%20or%20any%20other%20value%2Dgenerating%20activity.>

⁴ <https://www.opengroup.org/soa/source-book/intro/index.htm>

architecture design, but also links the development of both the service portfolio and the cyberinfrastructure. The need to carefully design service workflows relies on the critical role it plays in understanding the structure and functioning of eLTER services. The service workflows help identify not only which service elements are involved and the technical infrastructure they rely on but also define the processes that support service delivery — including roles, responsibilities, and tasks. Furthermore, they can be used to map the dependencies across different services, Topic Centres, and third-party providers. This comprehensive view is essential to ensure that the various components of the eLTER service landscape are well-coordinated and operate as seamlessly as possible.

Beyond supporting service alignment, service workflows are also key to system engineering efforts — particularly in preparing for potential challenges and risks during the transition to the operational RI phase as ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium). Since the final composition of member countries is still unknown, their financial contributions remain uncertain. This uncertainty has direct implications for available budget, which in turn could affect service levels, result in the scaling back of certain services, or even lead to the discontinuation of some offerings. Moreover, the risk exists that potential service providers may withdraw from the process before the establishment of the eLTER RI as ERIC, due to strategic shifts, funding issues, or other unforeseen reasons. Service workflow specifications enable eLTER to assess which other services might be affected by such changes and to understand the knock-on effects. This allows for proactive planning, scenario simulation, and the identification of mitigation strategies to ensure continuity and resilience of the overall infrastructure, even under constrained or changing conditions.

1.1. Project context: the legacy of eLTER PLUS and eLTER PPP

High-quality, reliable data is crucial for scientific research and the monitoring and improvement of environmental policies, both in Europe (Mirtl, 2010) and globally (Mirtl et al., 2018). For effective information sharing, data must be discoverable, with accessible metadata (Michener et al., 1997), and should be interoperable and reusable (FAIR principles, Wilkinson et al., 2016). This also involves improving the comparability and preservation of long-term ecological data (Vanderbilt et al., 2015).

The eLTER RI is designed to support long-term, interdisciplinary environmental research across Europe applying a holistic approach. At its core lies a structured data architecture (see Section 1.2) that facilitates the collection, processing, curation, and dissemination of environmental data to a diverse set of stakeholders.

The eLTER EnRich project builds on the foundation of two major H2020 projects that have been running in parallel since 2020, with the goal of planning and making the future eLTER RI operational by 2027. These projects focus on both the organisational and research aspects of the research infrastructure (RI). eLTER PPP primarily addresses organisational issues, business models, and the legal framework, while also identifying and planning the services that will form the RI's service portfolio. In contrast, eLTER PLUS contributes by aligning those services with the key research challenges identified by the scientific community involved in designing and implementing the RI.

Figure 1. EnRich links to PPP and PLUS and the WPs – Tasks – Matrix (PERT chart): LEFT MARGIN: Interactions with PPP and PLUS: EnRich digests, prioritises and steers targeted implementations. CENTRE & RIGHT SIDE: - Each stack of coloured arrows represents a Theme with two consecutive WPs over the project runtime - Each of the 2–3 Tasks per WP in period 1 has a corresponding task in the follow-up WP in period 2. - So, each coloured arrow represents a pair of corresponding tasks; - The bottom line of the graph explains the information provided for the pairs of corresponding tasks (in coloured arrows)

Both projects offer inputs that have been evaluated and validated through an ongoing, extensive consultation process. Figure 1 demonstrates how eLTER EnRich integrates the outcomes of the PPP/PLUS into the roadmap for RI implementation. In this report, the PPP project contributes by aligning the service portfolio with the stakeholder landscape, providing insights on user requirements, motivations, objectives, and strategies, and laying the groundwork for service provision. The primary source of information for the design of workflows that ensure the service provision is contributed by the PLUS project. Through the service specifications, details are provided that are useful for the implementation of the eLTER Cyberinfrastructure.

The eLTER PLUS project has collected data and ICT requirements (Peterseil et al., 2020), focusing on new data collections and the integration of historical data from eLTER sites and platforms (Peterseil et al., 2022). Key workflows that need to be supported by the eLTER CI have also been identified (Belleflamme et al., 2023).

All these requirements are essential for guiding future developments and should be incorporated into cohesive models that inform the design and implementation of core data services. In this report, our approach is to build these models as workflows encoded in a formal language, aiming to unify the representation of the knowledge by working groups in the PPP and PLUS projects.

Currently, the two projects describe their services using distinct communication strategies. The description in the PPP project is primarily textual, establishing context by focusing on general requirements, including stakeholder mapping and cost estimation, and referring broadly to existing components within a future CI for implementation. The primary audience in this case is the Interim Council, and the description is designed to provide an overview of the service, highlighting both its advantages and the complexities involved in its provision. In contrast, the PLUS project delves into technical specifics, examining the technology landscape in detail and aiming to thoroughly outline potential implementation solutions. It addresses ICT teams or more generally, the working groups responsible for the implementation and the provision of the services.

It is worth mentioning that those descriptions, i.e. the textual and the graphical ones, focusing on general requirements and on ICT requirements respectively, are of course overlapping, although with different levels of technical detail, but they both contain specific elements which are not evidenced in the alternative representation.

In the present report we aim to merge the two representations and use a consistent schema to gather all the available information in a comprehensive picture.

Based on discussions with the ICT team, it became clear that previous workflows and service models (e.g., D10.2, D10.3, D4.3) were complicated by a mix of processes, data flows, services, and physical and IT components. These models lacked a consistent schema to unify the various levels of interaction required for a complex CI like the one needed by eLTER RI.

To this purpose, based on feedback from the development team, we have chosen the ArchiMate framework, which offers both a schema and a machine-readable language suitable for our semantic representation purposes. The choice of a formal language is key to design the service workflows as instances of the processes identified and described by the System Engineering team and to facilitate the collaboration among the teams. The aim is here to align the ontologies and terminologies used by all the teams involved in the EnRich project to easily switch among different views of the same service (e.g. value chain, business role, architecture design, technology, operational stages etc.).

To set the scene for this representation, in the following sections we briefly introduce the cyberinfrastructure architecture that is at the core of the eLTER RI, and the core services it will provide. We then recall the frame of reference for our semantic representation of the workflows that enable the core services.

1.2. eLTER RI Cyberinfrastructure

To effectively address the research challenges encountered by the scientific community, it is essential to prioritise data, along with its management, processing and provision, at the core of service delivery. This requires both a conceptual model and a physical infrastructure represented here by the facilities of the eLTER Site and Platforms network and by the ICT components. The eLTER RI Cyberinfrastructure (CI) serves as the overarching framework that enables this integration and serves as the technical backbone for data management and information services within the eLTER RI.

According to the definition adopted in the eLTER EnRich project the eLTER RI Cyberinfrastructure (hereafter CI) *“supports distributed computing and information processing services like advanced data acquisition, -storage, -management, -integration, -mining and -visualisation. In scientific usage like in eLTER, CI is a technological and sociological solution to the problem of efficiently connecting laboratories, data, computers, and people, enabling derivation of novel scientific theories and knowledge in ecosystem science. CI is a sub-system of the wider eLTER RI System Architecture, and linked to IT and ICT infrastructure, which also covers hardware components.”*

The design and implementation of the CI is the continuation of the original roadmap for eLTER ICT and service innovation (Abbrent et al., 2024). Figure 2 represents the current view of a possible CI Architecture Model which represents the synthesis of work done in eLTER PLUS and eLTER PPP projects and is a result of the joint effort of a cross -transdisciplinary community.

Figure 2. Initial version of the eLTER Cyberinfrastructure Architecture Model version 1.2

The eLTER infrastructure includes a suite of interconnected components that support the discovery, access, and management of environmental research data. The eLTER Service Portal (SP) serves as the main entry point, offering access to services, spotlighted datasets, and personalized dashboards. The eLTER Discovery and Visualisation tool (DiV) enables interactive exploration of eLTER sites and datasets through map- and filter-based views. The eLTER Digital Asset Registry (DAR) records digital assets from eLTER and third parties, supported by automatic quality control. The eLTER Site Registry (DEIMS-SDR) functions as a metadata editor and registry, allowing operators to publish and manage site information. The eLTER Vocabulary service

maintains controlled terminologies, definitions, and multilingual mappings such as EnvThes. eLTER AAI (Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure) manages user identities, roles, and permissions in alignment with European and global systems. eLTER DataLabs provide virtual research environments, simplifying access to eLTER datasets for prototyping and developing advanced data products. Lastly, eLTER Central Data Nodes (CDN) offer domain-specific solutions for data quality assurance, metadata enrichment, and access via APIs. Together, these components create a robust framework for supporting FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data practices and advancing environmental research across Europe and beyond.

1.3. eLTER Service Portfolio

eLTER RI comprises two main pillars: 1) **physical network (National Research Infrastructures - NRI)** distributed across the partner countries which consist of **eLTER Sites** which foster research on the combined long-term effects of stressors on ecosystem functioning and **LTSER Platforms** that are regional-scale living labs for research on long-term human-environment interactions enabling transdisciplinary socio-ecological research. The common denominator is the realisation of the Whole System Approach in research and observation; and 2) **Central Services grouped in Thematic Service Areas (TSA)** which will be delivered through service-oriented Topic Centres. These TSAs are thematic groups of potential services. A given area might in the end be covered by one Topic Centre, but in general the Thematic Service Areas are a means to present and discuss how eLTER services could be grouped highlighting logical and functional dependencies. Ultimately, users will be able to access all services through a Service Portal (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Overview of eLTER RI design and elements provisioning the central (left) and distributed (right) services

A comprehensive description of the whole service portfolio has been provided in a deliverable of the PPP projects (Mallast et al, 2024) and integrates also the preliminary delivery specification to be satisfied by the Topic Centres.

Not all the services will enter the initial stage of the RI implementation. Therefore, a prioritisation has been done differentiating in 'Core' and 'Other' services. 'Core' services are a basic set of services that will enable eLTER RI operation and maximise its impact at an early stage. Complementary, 'other' services are a set of services that will enrich eLTER RI operation and maximise its impact over the long run. Table 1 lists the core services which will be the first ones to be implemented. These focus on Data management & integration (TSA01), Optimised Design and RI Interoperability (TSA02), and Head Office (TSA07).

Table 1 Overview of the core services belonging to 3 Thematic Service Areas

Thematic Service Area	Central services
Data management & integration (TSA01)	Site Registration and Cataloguing
	Access to SO Data
	Data ingestion and quality assurance
	Site Information Cluster
	Data Usage Statistics
	Site and Network Information
Optimised Design and RI Interoperability (TSA02)	Establishment and continuous updating of eLTER Standard Observations with related methods and protocols
	Contributing to the site selection and labelling service
	Technical consultation for new eLTER RI members on site locations and requirements
Head Office (TSA07)	Consulting and interfacing between scientific outcome (research, researchers, data) and users
	Project development and support
	Support of external reporting and assessment
	Communication and Promotion
	Partnerships and liasoning
	High-level representation, promotion and strategic alliances
	Promoting access (not (yet) considering support for visitors)
	NRI & community development and management
	Management, governance and steering across eLTER RI components
	Service portal/helpdesk operation and iterative improvement
	Competence building and staff training
	Strategic RI planning and improvement based on internal and external feedback
	Provisioning of socio-ecological Standard Observations
Site and Platform Forum	

To guide future developments, we have systematically broken down and modelled Core Services to serve as a blueprint for mapping all workflows of both remaining Core and Other Services that form the current eLTER service portfolio. In the present report we focus primarily on data management services (TSA01), which constitute the main asset of the RI, and on the Optimised Design and RI Interoperability services (TSA02).

2. Formalization of the service knowledge base: the ArchiMate framework

ArchiMate is an open, independent Enterprise Architecture standard (Lankhorst M. et al, 2017) that supports the description, analysis, and visualisation of architecture across business domains. It is hosted by The Open Group and fully aligned with TOGAF. ArchiMate helps stakeholders evaluate the impact of design decisions and changes.

In our case the “Enterprise” whose architecture we want to address is the Research Infrastructure to be analysed in its capability to provide services to a wide range of stakeholders. In doing so we aim also to harmonise the service provision, in particular with respect to data services, to the ENVRI Reference Model (de la Hidalgo et al, 2020).

In the description of the ENVRI Reference Model it is stated that *“Research Infrastructures are often complex distributed systems. Describing their structure and external properties is required to understand and manage these systems. When the system description concentrates on the distillation of general principles, it is called architecture. However, if the description is presented in a way that is useful for the derivation of a whole family of systems, it is called a framework. Hence, when describing a system supporting a broad range of applications, it is common to talk of an architectural framework. In this sense, the ENVRI Reference Model is an architectural framework for the design of a distributed system for environmental research infrastructures.”*

Although the construction of the architectural framework of eLTER RI is also demanded for other tasks within EnRich project, in the present report we strive to be consistent with the key concepts and terminology adopted within the ENVRI Reference Model, by embedding the semantics of the Reference Model into the ArchiMate ontology, as described in the following sections.

2.1. Defining components and layers

In enterprise architecture modelling, understanding the fundamental components and their relationships is essential for effective design, analysis, and communication across business, application, and technology domains. The ArchiMate⁵ language (Hosiailuoma., 2022) offers a robust framework for describing these components through a structured, service-oriented framework.

This framework organises the architecture into distinct layers, each focusing on a specific aspect of the enterprise while maintaining a consistent connection to other layers. These layers allow for a clear division of concerns, facilitating better management and alignment between business goals, cyberinfrastructure, and operational systems. Within these layers, key entities such as actors, roles, services, products, and nodes operate. Actors and roles represent the active participants in various layers, while services and products signify what is offered or produced. Additionally, entities and nodes function as structural components that house or carry out processes. Understanding how these components interact within and across layers enables stakeholders to model, analyse, and adapt enterprise architecture in response to business requirements and technological changes. Figure 4 provides an overview of the key elements of the framework grouped according to different information layers they belong to. A colour coding facilitated the reading of the schema.

This chapter introduces and defines a unified language for representing the various layers, actors, services, products, and structural elements, along with their relationships, within the ArchiMate schema. This common framework is essential for capturing and managing the complexity of the eLTER project, allowing for a clear and consistent depiction of its enterprise architecture.

⁵ ArchiMate® 3.2, Open Group, 2022. <https://pubs.opengroup.org/architecture/archimate32-doc/>

Figure 4. Overview of the ARCHIMATE schema (Hosiainluoma, 2022).

2.2. Layers

In the ArchiMate schema, certain layers are predefined. In this subchapter, we aim to create a dictionary that translates and organises the work done so far in the eLTER ICT development into the ArchiMate language model. This also enable translating from the ArchiMate layers back to the eLTER context, ensuring alignment between the two.

In Figure 5 shows the different layer categories in ArchiMate language which are further described in Table 2. Here we also provide the mapping to the terminology used in the eLTER context. In the following chapters of the report on the reference of the layers we refer to the terminology used for the eLTER layers.

Figure 5. The characterization of layers within the ArchiMate schema. In order top-down: Other, Business, Application, Technology, Physical, Motivation, Implementation & Migration

Table 2: Correspondence table between ArchiMate and ENVRI layers and eLTER layers.

ArchiMate Layer	eLTER Layer	ENVRI	Description	Components
Other	Other		Groupings, Course of Actions, Capabilities, Resources	Groups of things, Actions
Business	Services	Science	Human Components of Services	Actors, Roles
Business	Services	Information	Internal and external services such as Data Upload, Quality Check, Data Access	Processes, Actions, Products, Contracts, Services
Application	Application	Computational	All the interfaces needed to carry out the Services that interface with ICT	User Interfaces, APIs
Technology	ICT	Engineering	All the software part of eLTER CI, middleware	Software, Software Processes, Software Elements, Nodes, Networks
Physical	Physical	Technology	All the hardware part of eLTER CI such as servers, sensors, instruments, local terminals	Hardware, Sampling Tools, PCs

Motivation	Vision	Viewpoint specification e.g. System and context	The principle, the philosophy and the vision guiding all projects and its sub-processes	Stakeholder, Goals, Outcomes, Visions, Principles, Values
Implementation & Migration	Evolution		All the processes granting the possibility of keeping eLTER CI capable of change itself and adapt to new challenges	WPs, Deliverables, Implementation Events

2.3. Actors and roles

In this section, we identify the main roles who can interact with eLTER CI and serve as functional categories for how the actors engage with the system. Notably, an actor can assume multiple roles, and a role can be filled by various actors. For instance, a researcher involved in the project might take on the role of data provider for eLTER CI while also using the platform as a User. While the User role is accessible to all actors, some roles are restricted to specific actor types. In Table 3 we illustrate these correspondences.

Table 3: Roles according to D10.3 Plus, with 3rd Party roles in addition.

Group Role	Role	Description
Data User	Unregistered User	Main (external) actors using and accessing datasets and data products. Depending on the registration the access to data might be for browsing and visualize (unregistered) or for downloading (registered)
	Registered User	
Researcher	User/Provider	Researchers have a dual role in eLTER RI: they may provide data and knowledge and/or use the RI data and services, whether they are members of the eLTER community or not
Data (Collector and)Provider	Site Principal Investigator (SPI)	Are the main investigators at the eLTER facilities implementing the observations, recommendations, and requirements of the eLTER SO standard protocols and methods.
	3rd Party Data Provider (3PDP)	Are all 3rd party platforms contributing in collecting and organizing observations, generally following their own protocols and standards. (e.g. NasaPower, NOAA, NAOC, Citizen Scientists etc.)
Data Steward	DS Local (eLTER Facility)	Actors running and coordinating the process of creating, organising, and maintaining datasets to enable usability and accessibility (e.g., ensure consistency of metadata). This can be, depending on the organisation level of the eLTER facility, related to the scientific personnel or done by dedicated local data managers. Data curation is addressed on three different levels.
	DS National (LTER, NRI, ...)	
	DS eLTER RI	

	DS 3rd Party	Actors running and coordinating the process of creating, organising, and maintaining datasets according to their standards.
Data Storer	DStorer Local (eLTER Facility)	Main actors for the management and storage of the main eLTER data repository (eLTER Central Data Node) and providing the main facilities for cataloguing and discovery. Data management and provision is addressed on three different levels.
	DStorer National (LTER, NRI, ...)	
	DStorer eLTER RI	
eLTER Data Manager	eDM Coordinator	Main actors coordinating and planning the development of the architecture, services, and tools.
	eDM Operator	Team providing and prototyping the IT services for the project (e.g., staging area, eLTER CDN, DEIMS-SDR, B2SHARE, eLTER DIP, eLTER Vocab Server, eLTER Data Lab).
Site and Platform Coordinator (SPC)	Site Coordinator	Are the site/platform managers running the long-term monitoring and providing long-term in-situ data for the eLTER network and RI. They are the main contact points for the site
	Platform Coordinator	
National Coordinator	National Research Infrastructure (NRI) Coordinator	The National Coordinator manages and organises the national research infrastructure and network and provide the main contact to the national level.
European Coordinator	eLTER RI Head Office	Manages and coordinates the eLTER RI

Most of the group roles and the actors identified in the “Description” column of table 3 are the result of the activities performed in WP10 of the PLUS project. Two more groups have been added (Data Storer, eLTER Data Manager) to describe some parts of the service workflow, i.e. the data storage and governance, which are still under discussion and whose description might be updated in further development stages. In EnRich the terminology used to name the roles has been adjusted to be consistent with the Reference Architecture for FAIR Data Infrastructures⁶ and services, which is currently being adapted for the eLTER RI within the PLUS project. The results of this work, aimed at embedding FAIR principles by design, will contribute to the PLUS deliverable D10.4, titled ‘Technical Concept for Implementation of eLTER Standard Data Products’.

2.4. Building the workflows for “Data management & integration”: setting the scene

As evidenced by the description of the ARCHIMATE framework it is possible to construct the workflow of a service based on different views serving the purposes of both, the System Engineering approach and the design and implementation of the CI. The four pillars of a System Engineering approach can be resumed as: 1) technical management processes, 2) technical processes, 3) agreement processes, and 4) organisational

⁶

<https://github.com/amiika/fair-infrastructures?tab=readme-ov-file#reference-architecture-for-fair-data-infrastructures>

project-enabling processes (see figure 8). Of those pillars, the ones which are more tightly associated to the workflow design, are the technical processes. These include among the others, business or mission analysis, stakeholder needs and requirements definition, system definitions, architecture definition and implementation.

The first step of the technical processes, as evidenced in Figure 6, is the “business or mission analysis” which provides the motivation for the further development of a system. According to the ARCHIMATE schema, a model incorporating the business role analysis and the definition of stakeholder needs and requirements can be built as the combination of “motivation” and “strategy” layers/views.

These views have a low granularity (broad concepts, less technical details) and are a suitable recipient for the general information about the services provided by the PPP project. This is the proper granularity to handle the information to be exchanged with the System Engineering team. It is important to notice that while the System Engineering approach emphasises on the overall process required to plan and implement service delivery, the description and analysis of service workflows represent specific instances of some key steps within this process or provide inputs to process stages. While reconstructing the workflow in the ARCHIMATE framework, care is taken to ensure consistency with the overall representation provided by the System Engineering team. The next step is the upscaling of the workflow representation to include all the technical details necessary to inform the technological layer serving the purposes of the CI implementation.

Figure 6 Building block of the SE. Green bullets mark the elements which will be analysed in the first stage of the eLTER EnRich project

We consider here the starting point for an organisation aiming to provide services, whether it is an enterprise launching new products on the market or like in our case a research infrastructure generating services for different stakeholders’ categories. A business or mission analysis process is essential to develop a product (or service) vision that aligns with the organisation’s strategic goals. This process helps to clarify the objectives to be achieved and the motivations driving the definition and implementation of a new product or service. We exploit the outcomes of the analysis already conducted in the PPP and PLUS projects

(Gaillardet et al, 2021, Bäck et al, 2021) to implement a business analysis process on the TSA01 bundle gathering the core services supporting and implementing the eLTER RI data management and integration.

3. Thematic Service Area: Data Management and Integration

The TSA on Data Management and Integration provides a cohesive suite of functionalities that underpin the eLTER Research Infrastructure's ability to manage, disseminate, and track environmental data across its network of in-situ facilities. These services are designed to support the full data lifecycle, ensuring consistency, transparency, and accessibility for a wide range of users and stakeholders. At the foundation of this thematic area is the site registration and cataloguing service, which enables the systematic recording and publication of information regarding eLTER Sites and Platforms. This includes detailed metadata about observation locations, deployed sensors, and their affiliations with related networks and infrastructures, ensuring a robust and discoverable database of environmental research assets.

Data access is another core functionality, providing users with reliable access to quality-assured and integrated datasets from eLTER facilities. These datasets include Standard Observations and related contextual data, all supported by a centralized repository that manages quality assurance metadata to ensure scientific integrity and usability. To maintain high data quality standards, the data quality insurance service allows providers to submit raw or pre-cleaned datasets for validation. Through a centralized process with uniform criteria, this service ensures that submitted data meets eLTER's quality thresholds before being registered as standardized observations, promoting consistency and trust in the data offered.

The site information cluster service enhances data discoverability by offering access to both legacy and third parties' datasets. It is equipped with tools that support dynamic data retrieval and enable advanced operations such as data gap filling, thereby facilitating comprehensive temporal and spatial analyses.

In addition to access and quality, the thematic area includes a service dedicated to tracking data usage. This involves monitoring citations, data provenance, and usage metrics such as file downloads and user demographics. By using persistent identifiers, the system provides detailed statistics that reflect the reach and impact of publicly available eLTER data. Finally, the site and network information service ensures access to all essential site and network-level data required for national-level research infrastructure design and reporting. This function supports the planning and assessment processes by offering a consolidated overview of operational and structural elements within the eLTER network.

Together, these services form a robust and integrated system that supports efficient data stewardship, transparency, and the strategic development of the eLTER Research Infrastructure. These services and their supporting technical components, either directly or indirectly, benefit all stakeholders involved in the RI. In the following subsection we use the "Motivation" layer of the ArchiMate framework to perform a business analysis of the TSA linking the stakeholders' requirements to the expected outcomes and benefits coming from the implementation of the Data Management and Integration Services.

3.1. Motivations

First, to create a system capable of delivering new services, it is crucial to gather stakeholder needs and requirements (Gaillardet et al 2021). The stakeholder analysis is also the driving input for the definition of the "motivation layer" in the ARCHIMATE framework. It is worth to stress, that by **motivation** here we mean *"the motivation for the eLTER RI to engage in the provision of a given service bundle"* (Barov et al, 2021). We assume, that the endeavour of constructing new services has been preceded by an assessment of what are the main gaps, and the stakeholder needs which are not fully covered or satisfied by existing similar services.

In the following diagram (see Fig. 10), starting with six of the seven main stakeholder categories which resulted by the PPP analysis of the stakeholder landscape, we illustrate what are the drivers of the interest of each category in the TSA01 services, what are the assessments associated with those drivers and finally the goals the RI aims to achieve through the service provision. We have not included the stakeholder category, i.e. Research and Research Infrastructure funders, since many elements activated by the other categories apply to this last one too.

The representation also contains information about some of the “values” generated by the service. For the sake of clarity, the link of each value to each stakeholder category has been omitted since most of the “values” generated by the service are associated with many or all the stakeholders. Therefore, the values reported in Fig. 7 refer to the whole thematic service area leading to the value proposition for the individual services aggregated under the umbrella of TS01 which are described in the following chapter.

Figure 7. Motivation "view" underpinning the TSA01 provision

3.2. Value proposition and value chain

The value proposition for the whole TSA01 service bundle can be summarised as "*broker of validated and harmonised long-term, multi-scale data to support evidence-based environmental policy*" (Alam et al, 2025). The value proposition for each service is listed below and is derived from the internal discussion on service specifications carried out within the PPP/PLUS projects. It should be noted that at this stage the value proposition did not specifically address one or more stakeholder categories. The preliminary result of the analysis of the value which TSA01 can generate through the service provision is reported in the box below for each service of the bundle.

TSA01_DM.01 Site registration and cataloguing

This service will enable eLTER RI stakeholders to register, describe and search across site information through IT tools according to their needs. A persistent identifier (deims.id) for each facility is generated to unambiguously identify the facilities (e.g. in case of collocation). In addition, documentation of 'observation locations' and 'sensors' is enabled (identified by a stable URI). This service will also be a reference to the long-term observation facility as part of the provenance chain and to establish the site information clusters (TSA01 Service 05). The service will allow RI stakeholders and users to identify and select sites of interest according to the characteristics provided (e.g. discovery interface). This enables the management of the Transnational Access (TA) programme and access to site data (TSA01 Service 02 and Service 05).

TSA01_DM.02 Access to Site Data

This service will allow RI stakeholders to identify and (if available) download data through data services (complying with FAIR principles) for all available long-term observation data from eLTER facilities. The level of harmonisation and standardisation depends on the inclusion into core data workflows for SOs.

TSA01_DM.03 Data ingestion and quality assurance

This service will allow sites to gain greater promotion and dissemination of their data through validated and integrated eLTER data products. This will provide greater acknowledgement of environmental observation from each site and its collective value to the research community and wider eLTER stakeholders.

TSA01_DM.05 Site information clusters

This service will allow to : 1) provide a continuously updated and comprehensive landscape of relevant data sources relevant to address the eLTER research challenges; 2) facilitate the access to multiple data sources, removing technical barriers to the exploitation and re-use of data externally generated; 3) provide and store retrieval-based SOs and offer an on-demand service for browsing, downloading and clipping third parties data for specific research questions or to serve the purposes of synthesis toward actionable knowledge; 4) facilitate site data and external data resources to be merged to create an information cluster and made it available to eLTER RI stakeholders.

TSA01_DM.06 Data use statistics

This service will provide stakeholders with a measure of the use and impact of RI datasets and data products.

We further analysed the value chains for the different services listed under TSA01 and modelled it according to the ArchiMate framework. Figure 8 shows a structured view of a comprehensive TSA01 value chain which integrates the multiple value streams generated by the TSA01 services by using the ArchiMate language.

Figure 8. eLTER Value Chain for Data management and integration (TSA01) (consisting of multiple value streams)

The broader value chain in Figure 8 does not address individual services, instead it focuses on the structured pathway designed to ensure that environmental data is collected, processed, and used in a way that supports high-quality research and informed decision-making. Pre-condition for the process is the commitment to perform standardised observations that allow for consistent and meaningful monitoring and assessment of environmental change and ecosystem behaviour. This is the starting point of the value chain for TSA01 services, which is then broken into four main stages, each involving different stakeholders and responsibilities, with the primary goal of providing interoperable standard observations for monitoring environmental change:

- **Maintaining Site Infrastructure:** this first stage focuses on the foundational work of managing the physical and data infrastructure at monitoring sites through several sub-tasks under the responsibility of Data Collectors and Data Providers.
- **Maintaining FAIR Research Infrastructure:** the second stage ensures that the data collected is managed in accordance with the FAIR principles and supports data accessibility and usability through tools like persistent identifiers, data catalogues, and virtual research environments. This process is usually handled by Infrastructure Providers.
- **Providing Research Data Products:** here, the data is transformed into usable data products. This step includes quality control and is assisted by the research Data Stewards.
- **Using Data for Research and Decision-Making:** in the final stage, the data products are used by researchers and decision-makers to generate scientific insights and inform environmental policy.

Going back to the motivation view illustrated in Figure 7 we can place the generation of the value chain between the assessment and the goals. It describes how the planned structures should enable the RI to provide the added value(s). In other words, this is not about individual ICT requirements but rather developing and clarifying the purpose (motivation) which is the basis for the ICT requirements.

In summary, the value chain ensures that environmental observation data is not only collected responsibly but also curated, processed, and used in ways that make it actionable and impactful for science and society alike, enabling reproducible, reliable research and informed environmental governance.

3.3. The eLTER Data Lifecycle

This section provides a structured overview of the data lifecycle within TSA01 as represented in the ARCHIMATE model shown in Figure 9. The model is intended as a reference framework to support the interpretation of more detailed workflows described in the following chapter. It outlines the relationships between components relevant to the modelling of Data Management and Integration Services, highlighting the roles, interfaces, applications, and infrastructure nodes that enable and support these services and their subprocesses.

The data lifecycle begins with the collection of environmental observations at the eLTER Site Nodes (see Figure 9). These sites integrate a network of sensor systems—including both automated instruments and human-operated sampling (i.e., "human sensors")—to capture a broad range of ecological and climatic parameters. Data is either streamed in real time or temporarily stored before being transmitted to central systems, in accordance with defined observation protocols.

The initial stage of data handling is managed by the Data Collector and Provider, whose responsibilities include not only data acquisition and upload, but also the publication of data and definition of domain-specific models. This role is central to ensuring data is captured with appropriate context, scientific framing, and metadata, in alignment with a robust Data Management Plan.

Once data enters the CI, the Data Steward ensures its long-term usability and quality. Key responsibilities include:

- Ensuring adherence to data standards
- Overseeing data integration and interoperability
- Managing master and reference data
- Implementing quality control procedures
- Providing learning support and consultations

Data stewardship enables harmonisation and coherence across heterogeneous data sources, supporting their integration and reuse.

Data ingestion and harmonisation are facilitated through a Data Provider and Steward Interface, which serves as the entry point into the automated ingestion pipeline. Here, raw data is processed and aligned with internal schemas, enabling cross-site and cross-domain comparisons through the Data Harmonisation Pipeline. Subsequently, data enters the Processing Pipeline, where it is cleaned, enriched with metadata, and transformed into semantically enriched formats, ensuring its suitability for advanced analysis and reuse. The final stage of transformation is managed by the FAIR Publication Pipeline, which ensures full alignment with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles. Data outputs are stored as a FAIR Data Source and made accessible through the Digital Asset Registry (DAR). This interface allows a broad range of users - including researchers and policy-makers - to access quality controlled, harmonised, well-documented, and machine-readable datasets (and data products) via user-friendly tools.

It is important to note that, in this context, the term interface refers to more than a software component. It includes the design and functionality that mediate interactions between human users and digital systems, encompassing applications, workflows, and communication protocols required to support effective data governance.

Figure 9. Represents the elements of the TSA01 model and highlights the mutual service, realisation and dependency relationships.

The interface internally details the main applications necessary for the correct workflow of the detailed process. Some applications that already exist or that are not currently placed within an interface are represented externally (PIDer, DEIMS-SDR, EnvThes here representing the eLTER Vocab Server more in general, DAR). By PIDer we mean all those external services that can assign a Persistent Identifier, an example could be the ORCID or Zenodo platforms.

Two roles, which also provide a system oversight, support all these processes:

- The Data Storer, who manages storage systems and access interfaces
- The eLTER Data Manager, who oversees architectural coordination and service prototyping

These roles ensure, that the infrastructure runs smoothly, efficiently, and is adaptable to new research needs.

The eLTER data lifecycle exemplifies how collaboration and structured governance enhance data management. By integrating technological systems with clearly defined human roles, eLTER ensures that environmental data is not only collected and stored but curated and shared in ways that maximise its value for science and society.

The workflows presented in the following subsections are modelled based on the Reference Architecture for FAIR Data Infrastructures and services, under development in eLTER PLUS, specifically in WP11

In the following subsections we illustrate how the services belonging to the Data Management and Integration TSA (see Table 4) are positioned on the general workflow of Figure 9. The main roles, technologies and applications services involved in the provision of each specific service, are evidenced in darker colours. See table 4 for the list of the core services to be analysed together with a brief description of their main functionalities.

Table 4. Core services belonging to the TSA on Data Management and Integration (Mallast et al, 2024)

Core Service	Main Functionality
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Site Registration/Cataloguing (01_DM.01)	Registering and publishing information on eLTER in-situ facilities (eLTER Sites and eLTSER Platforms), AND on observation locations and deployed sensors AND affiliation of these facilities to related networks and other infrastructures
Data Access (01_DM.02)	Enables access to quality assured (QC), integrated data from eLTER in-situ facilities for Standard Observations (SO) and related contextual data (quality assurance codes on a central repository).
Data Quality Insurance (01_DM.03)	Enables data providers to have raw (level 0) or pre-cleaned data (level 1) data assured and registered with the eLTER RI through a centralised form with uniform criteria for the Standard Observations (level 2)
Site Information Cluster (01_DM.05)	Enables the discovery and provides access to Standard Observations (SO) and legacy data along with tools for dynamic retrieval of data, gap filling etc
Data Usage Statistics (01_DM.06)	Tracking citations of data published by eLTER RI with a PID-system, tracking of data provenance to data source level (with PIDs), tracking data usage (citations and quantitatively by downloaded files, downloaded PBs, and number of data users/institutions/countries etc.) and providing statistics about publicly available eLTER data
Site and Network Information (01_DM.08)	Enables access to all site and network information from within the eLTER RI that is needed for national network design and reporting purposes.

3.4. Site registration and cataloguing

Providing reliable documentation for observation facilities - such as LTER sites and LTSER platforms - is essential both for tracing the provenance and contextual background of environmental observations and for supporting the coordinated management of these facilities within the eLTER Research Infrastructure (RI). The Site Registration and cataloguing service is designed to support the comprehensive registration and FAIR-compliant publication of long-term ecological observation facilities. In addition to providing metadata for the standard observation (SO) data, this paves the way for remote and transnational access (RA and TA) to RI services. At its core, it uses a standardised information model to ensure that all documented facilities follow a consistent structure. This model captures key characteristics of each facility, such as its type, location, operational purpose and includes non-physical elements, such as measurement campaigns, network affiliations, and connections to broader research infrastructures.

To ensure that all documented elements adhere to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles, standardised information models are used. These models are linked to open vocabularies and

based on recommendations established by Wohner et al. (2020, 2022), as well as by relevant working groups.

The implementation of this approach is made possible through the Site Registration application service, highlighted in blue in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Workflow of TSA01.DM01: darker colours highlight the main components of the DM01 service within the TSA01 workflow model.

This eLTER RI Core Service provides a structured framework for the registration, publication, and management of observation facilities. It enables the recording of detailed metadata on long-term observation facilities using predefined, standardised models. In addition to documenting facility-level information, it supports the inclusion of metadata for observation locations and deployed sensors, which are linked to dataset records to form a complete provenance chain.

The service also captures information about the network and infrastructure affiliations of each facility, facilitating their integration within national and international frameworks such as LTER member networks or other co-located research infrastructures. Each documented entity—whether it’s a site, sensor, campaign, or affiliated network—is assigned a unique, persistent, and resolvable identifier, such as a PID, ensuring long-term traceability and accessibility.

Beyond registration, the service includes tools for managing observation facilities within the eLTER RI structure, particularly those categorised as level 1 and 2 facilities, while also supporting discovery and access to information on level 3 facilities. It offers a user-friendly interface for searching and selecting observation sites for editing or exporting metadata, as well as programmatic access through a REST API, enabling integration with other data services. DEIMS-SDR is the orchestrator of the service implementation.

Overall, this service forms a cornerstone of the eLTER RI, ensuring centralised yet collaborative documentation of observation facilities. Information is maintained centrally but provided by networks and site principal investigators themselves. The resulting data feeds into the eLTER information cluster and site catalogue, serving as a comprehensive, one-stop resource for researchers, infrastructure managers, and policy stakeholders alike.

3.5. Access to Site Data

The DM02 service focuses on how data flows from site-level collection to centralised, standardised access points. The darker-coloured components in the diagram of figure 11 serve as key references to the narrative, emphasizing the eLTER RI’s commitment to delivering quality-assured (QC) data and aligning with FAIR principles—ensuring that data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

Figure 11. DM02 - Access to Site Data.

One of the central features is the FAIR Data Source, represented in dark blue, which plays a pivotal role in granting access to high-quality, integrated datasets derived from standard observations and enriched with contextual metadata. This element supports the core objectives of the FAIR framework and is consistent with the European Commission’s open science agenda. Supporting this are elements like the Data Harmonisation Pipeline and Cleaned Data Source, which transform raw inputs into QC-compliant data streams that feed into the FAIR Data Source. Additionally, DEIMS-SDR and DAR - also marked in dark blue—serve as access points to a central data and metadata catalogue.

3.6. Data ingestion and quality assurance

The data ingestion and quality assurance service play a critical role in supporting core data workflows within the eLTER Research Infrastructure (RI). We focus here on sample and sensor SOs, for which the data provision starts at the Site Node and involves Site data operators, both for the data collection and for the uploading of the data object. Figure 12 represents the data ingestion process following two possible sensor paths for the sensor SOs (streaming or bucket upload) and a path from data obtained by sampling. The service enables data providers to submit and manage Standard Observation (SO) data - whether in raw form (Level 0) or pre-processed form (Level 1) - by registering it with the eLTER RI. The process ensures that data entering the infrastructure follows a structured path toward quality assurance and harmonization.

Figure 12. DM03 - Data Ingestion and Quality Assurance.

A centralised quality control mechanism is applied to relevant variables within the Standard Observations, using consistent and transparent criteria. This process results in high-quality, quality-controlled observational data (Level 2), which represents a harmonised and reliable dataset ready for integration. When these data are incorporated into broader eLTER data products, eLTER ensures an additional layer of centralised quality control, safeguarding the consistency and integrity of composite datasets. The general application services for data processing are highlighted in relation to the scientific production workflow and quality assurance.

The final outputs are made available through FAIR-aligned data services, which include features for proper data citation and detailed tracking of data provenance and processing history. This ensures transparency in data treatment and supports reproducibility of research.

Overall, this service is a foundational element of the eLTER infrastructure, as it underpins the commitment to delivering high-quality, standardised, and interoperable data.

3.7. Information Clusters

The primary objective of this service is to facilitate the discovery and access of “retrieval-based” Standard Observations (SOs) that originate from external sources, such as national statistical offices or Earth Observation (EO) data providers. Beyond these main sources, the service is designed to accommodate additional data types and sources not currently represented in the existing SO list, allowing for a broader and more dynamic integration of relevant datasets into the eLTER Research Infrastructure (RI).

Key functionalities of the service include the registration of relevant retrieval-based data sources in the eLTER Data Access Registry (DAR), particularly those identified as valuable by the internal research community and made available for data reuse. This ensures a curated and accessible repository of third-party data that supports scientific activities across sites and platforms.

The service also provides rich metadata for each registered source, detailing access conditions (e.g., open access, registration-based, fee-based, or under specific licensing terms), as well as technical specifications such as data format, spatial and temporal resolution, and update frequency. These metadata help researchers quickly assess the usability and relevance of a given dataset for their specific needs.

Figure 13. DM05 - Information Cluster.

In addition to metadata and discovery, the service offers practical tools to enhance data usability. These include capabilities to spatially clip data according to site boundaries, mechanisms to request and obtain third-party data on demand, and advanced tools for dynamic data retrieval targeted at experienced researchers who require real-time or programmatic access.

Furthermore, the service supports the assignment of persistent identifiers (PIDs) to eLTER-derived products, ensuring traceability, reproducibility, and proper citation, whenever licensing conditions of the original datasets allows re-publication. Data visualization features are also included, with the option to connect to or integrate existing visualization tools provided by third-party data sources, enhancing the user experience and enabling comparative analysis.

This service plays a vital strategic role within the eLTER RI. By extending the scope of data available for research at both site and platform levels, it supports efforts such as gap filling, contextual data enrichment, and the pursuit of new interdisciplinary research questions. It also strengthens collaboration opportunities by fostering synergies with European and global networks, infrastructures, and organizations, thereby enhancing the exploitation and interoperability of shared data resources.

3.8. Data use statistics

This service enables data providers to access usage statistics for data they have registered with the eLTER RI, as well as any data products derived from that data (Figure 14). The primary focus is on citation metrics rather than views or downloads, to assess the impact of eLTER data more meaningfully.

It is intended to support tracking of citations for data objects published by eLTER RI through a persistent identifier (PID) system. Additionally, it allows for tracing data provenance down to the source level using PIDs, monitoring data usage through citation counts and quantitative indicators such as the number of downloaded files, total volume in petabytes, and the number of data users, institutions, or countries. The service should also provide statistics on publicly available eLTER data, facilitating comparisons with actual usage statistics.

All these capabilities are closely linked to the data policy, terms of use, and the availability of data which can be accessed through APIs.

Figure 14. DM06 - Data Usage Statistics.

A potential pathway toward implementing a service for tracking data use statistics could begin with a minimum viable product focused on collecting and visualising data download statistics. These statistics can be automatically extracted from backend log files of the download service, eliminating the need for developing a separate download tracking feature. Instead, implementation costs would be embedded within the overall development of the research infrastructure's backend system—whether it is database-driven or hosted on a cloud platform. In this form, the MVP is not an independent service but an integrated function that supports the user interface or website displaying usage data.

As development progresses, data usage tracking can be expanded beyond simple download metrics. Additional insights can be gained by analysing user behaviour, such as identifying the origins of data queries and the types of data requested. Achieving this requires consistent and structured naming conventions within the data source, enabling the configuration of analytics tools to monitor interactions, such as which links are clicked. Tools like the open-source Matomo (Hopkins.fi) offer a feasible solution for implementing this level of digital analytics.

A further layer of complexity involves tracking data citations. The foundation for this is the publication of clear data citation guidelines and encouraging users to follow them when referencing data. Various methods exist for identifying and monitoring citations in scholarly outputs, enabling a more qualitative measure of data impact.

A more advanced implementation could involve assigning DOIs to individual data products, which can reference original data sources. This could be extended further to assign DOIs to smaller data objects or even to specific downloads, enhancing transparency, reproducibility, and alignment with FAIR data principles. However, realizing this level of provenance tracking and citation monitoring would require a dedicated service. Such a service would necessitate detailed planning before costs could be reasonably estimated.

Looking ahead, recent developments by DataCite offer promising support for this direction. With funding from the Wellcome Trust, DataCite is building the Open Global Data Citation Corpus—an initiative aimed at transforming the data citation landscape. This corpus will collect asserted citations from a wide array of

sources and be accessible to all community stakeholders. By aggregating data references across research outputs, the corpus will enhance the ability to track impact, guide funding decisions, and improve the visibility and dissemination of scientific data.

4. Thematic Service Area: Optimal Design and RI interoperability

The functioning and the continuous update of the RI requires services which focus on the evolution of the internal organisation as well as on keeping the RI updated with respect to broadening of the scope of research activities, emergence of new technologies and opportunities, possible increase in size and different distribution of the service provision. This task is delegated to the service bundle TSA02.OD responsible for the optimisation of the RI design. We analyse here only the services that have been included in the list of the Core Services and are resumed in Table 5 together with the main functionalities associated to them. These services are also strictly related to the data services provided by the CI and might have an impact on the technical implementation.

Table 5. Core services belonging to the TSA02 on Optimal Design and RI Interoperability (Mallast et al, 2024)

Core Service	Main Functionality
Updating of eLTER Standard Observations (02_OD.01)	Periodic revision of methods and protocols, discussion of adapting new methods/protocols with eLTER coordination as well as maintaining and updating repository of documents and/or videos describing the protocols and providing a consultation service for questions/requests from Site and Platform coordinators on SO protocols.
Site selection and labelling (02_OD.05)	Manages the site labelling process. Evaluates the representativeness of the eLTER network of labelled eLTER in-situ facilities and identifies spatial gaps to allow an optimal SO coverage and regarding eLTER WAILS approach and suggests eLTER RI coordination to establish/upgrade eLTER in-situ facilities to new categories (Cat 1/ Cat 2) to fill gaps
Technical consultation: New eLTER RI members (02_OD.07)	Manages consultation process to ensure assessment of SO's, their location and requirements at site, national and regional level and provide a pre-evaluation of proposed sites according to the geographical/biome/ecosystem type coverage of the whole RIs (consideration of strategic positioning and added value for the eLTER RI)

4.1. Motivations

The following diagram (see Figure 15) contains the motivation view behind the core services of the bundle. It is a simplified version focusing on the stakeholders most impacted by the service implementation, which in this case are the scientific community, peers in environmental research and observation, decision-makers and internal community.

Figure 15. Motivation view of TSA01.OD

In the following subsections we provide a representation in the ARCHIMATE language of the 3 Core Services belonging to TSA02.

4.2. Establishment and continuous updating of eLTER Standard Observations with related methods and protocols

With reference to the System Engineering approach this service is associated with the process management as well as with the maintenance, although not necessarily at a technical level. The aim of this service is to gather all the information about existing and new methods and protocols and to inform the RI decision processes. The way this service contributes to decisions, and the information flow is streamlined into the CI needs to be better specified. The following diagram illustrates a possible workflow to establish these connections. First, we must identify the starting point and the roles. We assume that the executive team under the coordination of a process manager starts the revision process and keeps a technological watch on new opportunities. That requires also an analysis of costs and benefits of the changes to be proposed. The outcome of the preliminary analysis is to trigger a discussion with the Head Office, the expert group and the

SPF, with the aim of generating a sustainable plan for changes. The implementation of the plan involves a collaboration with the management of TSA01 to feed in the CI the new methods and protocols. These changes have an impact on the Data Ingestion and the metadata profile, including changes in the data models, reduction or incrementation of the number of observations, new sources of third parties' data to be added, new APIs and so on. It is of utmost importance that the decisional process and the exchange of information with the data services is properly managed. In figure 20 we provide a simplified diagram of a potential workflow for this service.

Figure 16. Representation of the workflow of the TSA02_OD.01 service

4.3. Contributing to the site selection and labelling service

The services provided by the Research Infrastructure (RI) also encompass activities related to the reconfiguration of the entire network, including the integration of new sites and the upgrade or downgrading of existing facilities. Within this framework, the establishment of new sites and the labelling of both new and existing sites constitute the primary objectives of the TSA02.OD.05 service. This service can be articulated through two principal workflows: the monitoring workflow and the labelling workflow.

The monitoring workflow focuses on the continuous oversight of the network to ensure that all sites and platforms maintain adequate performance levels and comply with the eLTER standards appropriate to their assigned category. It is anticipated that, at regular intervals, the overall distribution of sites will undergo review to detect gaps in spatial coverage or areas insufficiently represented in relation to specific research priorities or thematic knowledge domains. When such deficiencies are identified, corrective actions may include upgrading the classification of existing sites, expanding the network by establishing new sites, or pursuing co-location opportunities with other Research Infrastructures (RIs) or networks. These strategies aim to optimise both time and resource efficiency.

The monitoring cycle also serves to periodically assess the performance of existing sites, ensuring their ongoing compliance with technical standards and the renewal of institutional commitments. Adjustments to site or platform categories may be recommended based on the actual fulfilment of technical requirements. The upper portion of Figure 17 presents a summary of the monitoring workflow.

Several roles are integral to the monitoring workflow, including the National Research Infrastructure (NRI), the Head Office, and the General Assembly. The overall coordination of the process is managed by the Topic Centre, which hosts a Thematic Committee and an Executive Board. The Topic Centre appoints a Labelling

Review Committee responsible for executing the key processes involved in both the monitoring and labelling workflows. The monitoring process is conducted systematically every five years and is driven by the analysis of Operation Reports submitted by the NRIs. These reports inform the production of a comprehensive review of the network's status, possible amendments to the existing Labelling Plan, and the formulation of proposals for potential co-location initiatives with other RIs.

The final output of the monitoring workflow is an Assessment Report prepared by the Head Office, with analytical support from the Labelling Review Committee. This Assessment Report is submitted to the General Assembly, which holds the authority to make the final decisions regarding network configuration and strategic developments. Moreover, any expansion of the network requires updates to the data services managed by the Cyberinfrastructure (CI), particularly those related to site registration and cataloguing services predominantly operated through DEIMS-SDR. In designing these data services, it is crucial to minimise the operational impact associated with ongoing updates and system changes.

The labelling workflow, detailed in the lower portion of Figure 16, involves the same set of actors. This process is initiated by the National Research Infrastructure, which submits a Pre-label Report containing a proposal for the establishment or upgrade of a research site. The Labelling Review Committee evaluates the Pre-label Report, undertaking a detailed verification of the site's compliance with the required technical and design standards. Based on this assessment, the proposal is either approved or rejected.

If the proposal does not meet the necessary standards, it enters a revision cycle whereby the NRI addresses the technical recommendations issued by the Labelling Review Committee. The revised proposal is then resubmitted for evaluation. If the proposal is approved, the site is formally integrated into the eLTER network. At this stage, the Head Office assumes responsibility for compiling a Labelling Review Approval Package, which is subsequently presented to the General Assembly for formal ratification. Like the monitoring workflow, the addition of a new site necessitates updates to the data services managed by the CI, ensuring consistency and accuracy across the network's registry and catalogues.

The entire architectural model underscores a highly structured, transparent, and dynamic process, wherein proposals and scheduled evaluations systematically guide the development, maintenance, and evolution of a robust research network. This integrated approach ensures sound governance, fosters continuous improvement, and secures the long-term quality and relevance of the eLTER infrastructure.

Details on the procedures for the implementation of the service in the pilot stage and for the final set up are contained in the PPP deliverable D6.3 "Site Labelling process and procedure for the implementation" by F. Pando et al. (2024).

Figure 16. Representation of the workflow of the TSA02_OD.05 service

4.4. Technical consultation for new eLTER RI members on site locations and requirements

The workflow of service TSA01.OD.07 is related to the management and coordination of a consultation and evaluation process for selecting and integrating sites into the RI. The team in charge of providing the service engages with Research Infrastructure members and experts to identify and understand the needs and challenges concerning site location and environmental monitoring requirements. The objective is to evaluate potential sites for their strategic value and alignment with the RI's geographical, biome, and ecosystem coverage objectives. The evaluation includes several actions: a) analyse the proposed sites against established criteria (e.g., diversity, representativeness of ecosystems, geographical spread); b) identify gaps in coverage and assess how each site contributes to the overall RI network's goals; c) prioritise sites that provide strategic positioning or unique contributions, such as filling coverage gaps or representing underrepresented biomes. The request for additional sites may reach out the team via the CI help desk and might be elaborated using applications already exploited in other services of the same bundle. The outcome will be a report which will be used by the Head Office to take decisions. In case the new site is approved, this process goes through the Interim Council and the new configuration of the network will be integrated in the CI.

Among the services designed by the team there is also to facilitate knowledge transfer and capacity building by connecting less experienced sites with established RI member networks. These tutoring activities will exploit the knowledge base of the RI which might be also accessed via the help desk. In Figure 17 we illustrate the main roles and functions included in the service workflow.

Figure 17. Representation of the workflow of the TSA02_OD.07 service

5. Conclusions and steps forward

This report presents a consolidated overview of the ongoing implementation of the core services within the eLTER RI. The information has been drawn from diverse sources and continuously refined through iterative feedback from key contributors, including NRIs, the Interim Council, teams from the PLUS and PPP projects, and, most notably, the ICT team, which plays a central role in establishing the technological infrastructure underpinning service delivery. The outcome of this collaborative effort is a set of workflows that extracts essential information related to a selected group of core services.

It is important to note that the current depiction is neither exhaustive nor definitive. Rather, it reflects a work in progress that must evolve through a flexible and iterative governance model grounded in Agile principles. Such a model enables ongoing feedback, regular refinement of workflows based on operational experience, and continuous enhancement, thereby ensuring that service provision remains aligned with evolving scientific and societal needs.

Advancing the development of eLTER RI service workflows requires a well-orchestrated and structured approach. This includes strengthening governance frameworks, enhancing technical integration, fostering meaningful stakeholder engagement, and ensuring adaptability across all levels of the infrastructure. This includes establishing a robust governance framework that connects TSA01 Data Management with TSA07 Head Office services and developing an internal model for Cyberinfrastructure (CI) governance. Such a model should clarify federated responsibilities, define service levels, and ensure quality assurance across distributed service nodes, all under the transparent oversight of the Head Office.

A further step involves clearly defining how the Head Office interacts with the CI, particularly in managing and approving changes to workflows, datasets, and network configurations. To support effective change management, there must be well-structured processes for identifying stakeholder needs and translating them into evolving goals. These processes should outline how multiple roles or organisations coordinate when changes are introduced, with responsibilities and constraints precisely assigned to each actor.

To maintain service quality and responsiveness, it is recommended that a structured review and update mechanism be implemented. Regular review cycles should be established in advance to manage updates related to service objects (SOs), site labelling, and network expansion or reconfiguration. By predefining these cycles, the system can ensure ongoing adaptability while avoiding overburdening the Head Office and associated coordination teams.

As services vary significantly in their maturity, another critical step is to refine those workflows that are still evolving. This involves systematically mapping existing workflows, identifying gaps, and clarifying associated roles, timelines, and necessary competencies. When network changes occur—such as the addition or upgrade of sites—it is vital that the corresponding updates to CI services are synchronised, particularly for site registration and cataloguing, to safeguard data integrity and discoverability.

Minimizing disruption during updates is also crucial. All modifications to CI services—such as those involving registration, cataloguing, and data access workflows—should be carefully planned to maintain operational continuity. Where possible, backward compatibility should be preserved, and any changes must be communicated clearly and in a timely manner to all affected stakeholders.

Another important step is to continue integrating lessons learned from the eLTER PPP and PLUS projects into ongoing service development. Best practices emerging from these initiatives should be distilled into standard operating procedures, especially in the areas of stakeholder engagement, change management, and cross-service interoperability.

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